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Comparative analysis of the Oxyfuel and Calcium looping processes for low-carbon cement production

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Abstract

In this work, the performance of a cement plant with the integrated calcium-looping (CaL) system being developed in the H2020 CLEANKER project are simulated and benchmarked against alternative CO₂ capture options, namely: (i) Tail-end CaL configuration (an end-of-pipe CaL option, with circulating fluidized bed reactors) (ii) Full Oxyfuel configuration (where both the pre-calciner and the rotary kiln are operated in oxy-combustion mode), and (iii) Partial Oxyfuel configuration (where only the pre-calciner is converted to oxy-combustion). Both CaL and oxyfuel options are integrated with a CO₂ purification unit (CPU). The analysis performed shows that CaL systems provide greater CO₂ reductions (both direct and indirect) than oxyfuel systems, but are subject to greater fuel consumption. The integrated CaL system shows better energy performance than the tail end CaL system (which is the most fuel consuming system) thanks to the presence of a single calciner. The full oxyfuel system shows the lowest SPECCA value among the systems studied but is penalized by the high electric energy demand. Finally, the partial oxyfuel system has lower electricity consumption than the full oxyfuel system, but it is the system with the highest CO₂ emissions.

Keywords: Ca-Looping; CCS; Oxyfuel; Partial Oxyfuel; Cement; CLEANKER

1. Introduction

Cement production is responsible for about 8% of the world's anthropogenic CO₂ emissions [1]. Being CO₂ emissions intrinsic to the clinker production process, the production of low-carbon cement relies on CCS. Most of the carbon capture technologies analysed and proposed so far are based on oxyfuel and post-combustion processes. A state-of-the-art cement plant has a specific CO₂ emission per ton of clinker produced of about 865 kg_{CO₂}/t_{clk} [2], about 60% of which is associated with the calcination reaction ($\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$). The CaO generated in the calcination process reacts with the other components of the raw meal, such as silica and alumina, to generate the constituents of clinker [2]. In a modern cement plant, about 90% of the calcination process takes place in a precalciner, while main clinker constituents are formed in the rotary kiln. Oxyfuel and Calcium looping (CaL) technologies are among the most promising technologies for CO₂ capture in cement plants. The CaL technology can be integrated in a cement kiln with two different configurations. The first, commonly proposed in the literature [3–7], is the tail-end CaL configuration, where the CO₂ capture system treats all the flue gas coming out of the preheating tower of the cement

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kiln. The second is the integrated CaL configuration, where the two reactors of the CaL system are integrated in the preheater of the cement plant and the carbonator treats only the flue gases leaving the rotary kiln [8]. As presented by De Lena et al [8], the integrated CaL configuration is preferable over the tail-end one from an energy point of view, thanks to the presence of a single calciner, which has the dual role of pre-calcining the solid materials entering the rotary kiln and regenerating the CO₂-sorbent used in the carbonator reactor. The aim of H2020 European project CLEANKER [9] is to demonstrate the technical feasibility of the integrated CaL configuration at TRL7 and to perform a techno-economic assessment of the process.

Oxyfuel technology is based on the idea of using pure oxygen instead of air as oxidant in the clinker burning process. The configuration most commonly proposed for this technology is the full-Oxyfuel configuration [10–12], where the combustion process is carried out with an oxidant flow composed mainly of O₂ and CO₂, in order to produce a flow rich in CO₂ that can be treated directly in the CO₂ purification unit (CPU). The aim of this work is to present a comparative technical assessment between different configurations of the Oxyfuel and CaL technologies for the production of low-carbon clinker.

Nomenclature

ASU	Air Separation Unit
CaL	Calcium Looping
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CFB	Circulating Fluidized Bed reactor
CPU	CO ₂ Purification Unit
EFR	Entrained Flow Reactor
IL	Integration Level
ORC	Organic Rankine Cycle
SPECCA	Specific Primary Energy Consumption for CO ₂ Avoided

Subscripts

clk	Clinker
e	Electric
eq	Equivalent
LHV	Lower heating value
ref	Reference

2. Method

The methodology used in this work is in accordance with the framework of the H2020 CEMCAP project [13]. All configurations considered in this work (for both CaL and oxyfuel cases) are analyzed from an energy-environmental point of view, though process simulations performed by combining several tools. The mass and energy balances of the CO₂ capture systems integrated in cement kiln have been estimated by the proprietary code GS [14] developed by the GECOS group of the Department of Energy at Politecnico di Milano. Assumptions related to the clinker burning line have been defined according to the model developed by the German Cement Works Association VDZ for the European Cement Research Academy (ECRA) [12] and the IEA Greenhouse Gas R&D Programme [15].

The simulation of CaL reactors is performed by using dedicated 1D models developed in Matlab:

- The model used to estimate the CO₂ capture performances of the EFR carbonator was developed by Spinelli et al. [16];
- The CFB reactor model used to estimate the CO₂ capture efficiency of the carbonator of the tail-end CaL configuration was developed in Matlab by Romano in [17].

The simulation of the CPU is carried out in Aspen Plus [18], using the model developed by Magli et al. and described in CLEANKER deliverable D5.10 [19]. The heat recovery steam cycle parameters are defined according to the thermal power available, as discussed in the CEMCAP Framework [20].

The comparative analysis between the various technologies was made by comparing the following KPIs:

- *Direct primary energy consumption* (q , MJ_{LHV}/t_{clik}) and *direct CO₂ emissions* (e_{CO_2} , kg_{CO_2}/t_{clik}), that indicate respectively the primary energy consumed through fuel combustion and the CO₂ directly emitted at the stack the cement plant per unit of clinker produced;
- *Indirect primary energy consumption* (q_e , MJ_{LHV}/t_{clik}) and *indirect CO₂ emissions* (e_{CO_2} , kg_{CO_2}/t_{clik}) that indicate respectively the primary energy consumption and the CO₂ emissions associated to the production the electricity used in the cement plant (P_e , MJ_e/t_{clik}) and are calculated according to the following equations:

$$q_e = \frac{P_e}{\eta_e} \quad ; \quad e_{CO_2,e} = P_e \cdot e_e$$

where the net electric efficiency and the specific CO₂ emissions ($\eta_e = 45.9\%_{LHV}$; $e_e = 262 \text{ kg}_{CO_2}/MWh_e$) are selected to represent the reference scenario for electricity generation, according to the average EU-28 non-CHP energy mix of year 2015;

- *Equivalent primary energy consumption* (q_{eq} , MJ_{LHV}/t_{clik}) and *equivalent CO₂ emissions* (e_{CO_2} , kg_{CO_2}/t_{clik}), obtained by summing the direct and indirect contributions;
- *Specific Primary Energy Consumption for CO₂ Avoided (SPECCA)* [MJ_{LHV}/kg_{CO_2}], which indicates the additional equivalent primary energy used to avoid a unit equivalent CO₂ with respect to the reference cement plant without a CO₂ capture system (*ref*):

$$SPECCA = \frac{q_{eq} - q_{eq \text{ ref}}}{e_{CO_2,eq \text{ ref}} - e_{CO_2,eq}}$$

3. Plants description

3.1. Reference cement plant

The reference cement plant without CO₂ capture relies on the Best Available Technique (BAT) standard as defined in the European BREF-Documents (Best Available Technique Reference) for the manufacture of cement [21] based on dry process configuration with a clinker production of about 3000 tpd. For a more accurate description the reader is addressed to the following articles [2,7].

3.2. Integrated Cal Configuration

The integrated CaL configuration (presented in Fig. 1) is based on two interconnected entrained flow reactors, using raw meal as CO₂ sorbent instead of pure limestone. For a comprehensive description of the process, the reader is addressed to [8].

Fig. 1 Schematic of the integrated CaL cement kiln

In this configuration the carbonator is an adiabatic, 120m-long refractory lined gooseneck reactor, fed with the flue gas leaving the rotary kiln (stream #5). The carbonator inlet temperature is controlled by cooling the recirculated solids in the sorbent cooler (#8). About 80% of the inlet CO₂ is captured in the carbonator. The flue gas from the rotary kiln is cooled in a two-stage raw meal preheater before entering the carbonator. The amount of raw meal fed to this preheater is tuned to achieve a gas temperature at preheater outlet and carbonator inlet (#6) equal to 434 °C, which allows achieving the target adiabatic mixing temperature of 600 °C of the solid-gas mixture at the carbonator inlet. The oxyfuel calciner represents both the cement kiln pre-calciner and the calciner of the CaL system, and it works under higher CO₂ partial pressure with respect to the reference air-fired pre-calciner. To ensure a calcination degree comparable with conventional air-fired calciners, an operating temperature of 920°C has been assumed. The oxyfuel calciner is fired with coal (#21) and a 30%vol. O₂ stream, obtained by mixing 95% pure O₂ from the ASU (#19) and a fraction of the calciner off-gas (#25), which is cooled to a temperature of 400 °C and then recirculated to the calciner inlet. Combustion provides the heat required for heating and calcining both the recarbonated sorbent (#7) and the preheated raw meal, which comes partly from the two-stage preheater (#4) and partly from a three-stage preheater (#3) using CO₂-rich calciner off-gas at 920 °C (#22) as heat source. A fraction of the calcined raw meal (42%) is sent to the rotary kiln (#32), partly (53%) sent to the carbonator after cooling in the sorbent cooler (#30) and partly (5%) entrained with the CO₂-rich gas from the calciner. The rotary kiln working condition is very similar to the baseline operation without CO₂ capture: the main burner remains in air-blown combustion mode, and the variation of the composition of the calcined raw meal fed to the rotary kiln is not significant. The heat available from the CO₂-rich stream, the III air and the CO₂-lean gas leaving the carbonator, is recovered and used for electricity generation in a steam cycle.

4. Alternative CO₂ capture processes

The CO₂ capture technologies chosen for the comparison are: (i) Tail-end CaL configuration, an end-of-pipe CaL option with circulating fluidized bed reactors, (ii) Full Oxyfuel configuration, where both the pre-calciner and the rotary kiln are operated in oxy-combustion mode, and (iii) Partial Oxyfuel configuration, where only the pre-calciner is converted to oxy-combustion. These technologies are analyzed from an energy and environmental perspective as discussed in section 2. A brief description of these processes is given below.

4.1. Tail-end CaL

In the Tail-end configuration (Fig. 2), the flue gas from the cement kiln is sent to the CaL system, which is then built in the cement kiln line as an end-of-pipe system. For a comprehensive description of the process, the reader is addressed to [7].

Fig. 2 Schematic of the cement kiln with Tail End CaL capture system

One of the advantages of the CaL technology is that most of the energy introduced into the calciner for regenerating the sorbent can be recovered at high temperature in the cooled carbonator and efficiently converted into electricity.

The gas leaving the preheater tower at about 330°C (stream #18) is treated in the carbonator of the CaL system, where about 90% of the CO₂ contained in the flue gas is removed. A fraction of the limestone fed to the cement kiln is introduced in the calciner of the CaL process to be used as a CO₂-sorbent. The CaO-rich solid purge from the CaL process is then introduced into the clinker burning line for replacing part of the limestone in the raw meal. The Integration Level (IL) is therefore defined as the percentage of Ca entering the clinker burning process with the CaL purge with respect to the total Ca fed to the plant.

The CO₂-lean gas leaving the carbonator (#20) exits at 650°C and is cooled to a temperature of about 430°C (#21) before its use in the raw mill for drying purposes. The carbonator works at the typical temperature of 650°C [22] and the solids exiting this reactor (#22) are sent to the CFB calciner, where oxy-combustion of coal is carried out to convert the CaCO₃ formed in the carbonator back to CaO. To ensure complete calcination, a calciner outlet temperature of 920°C is assumed. The ASU produces 95% pure oxygen to be used as oxidant in the CaL calciner. A CO₂ recycle (#13) acts as temperature moderator, by reducing O₂ concentration in the oxidant stream at calciner inlet down to 50%

5. Comparative analysis

5.1. Direct, Indirect and equivalent primary energy consumption

In all the configurations here envisaged, the *direct fuel consumption* increases, in particular:

- in full and partial oxyfuel configurations, the fuel burned in the cement kiln increases of +3% and +19% respectively. The primary energy consumption of the partial oxyfuel configuration is higher than presented in the ECRA study [12] because in this work all the configurations have been studied and compared for retrofit cases, while the ECRA partial oxyfuel configuration has been developed with the aim of maximizing the energy efficiency of the system, leading to different assumptions and plant configurations. As an example, in the present work the oxyfuel calciner has been simulated by tuning the CO₂ recirculation rate in order to keep the gas volume flow at reactor outlet unchanged with respect to its baseline operation, whereas the ECRA study envisages different gas volumes and a new design of risers and cyclones. In addition, O₂ input has been tuned to meet a concentration of 5%vol at calciner outlet, whereas the ECRA case features a lower oxygen content (3.2%vol). Finally, some differences are related to the assessment of the heat recovery sections: for instance, tertiary air is partially used in the preheating tower and partially exploited in the heat recovery section of the bottom cycle, whereas in the ECRA configuration this hot stream is entirely exploited to preheat the CO₂ recycle via a gas-gas heat exchanger. Due to these differences the overall energy consumption here presented is higher than what calculated for the optimized ECRA configuration.
- in the integrated CaL configuration, the direct fuel consumption increases by 67%, due to the dual role of the CaL calciner: (i) the production of the calcined material to be fed into the rotary kiln and (ii) the sorbent regeneration, which requires also to heat up the carbonated solids from 670°C to 920°C ;
- in the tail end configuration, the fuel input increase is about 170% and 119% in 20%-IL and 50%-IL respectively. The main reason is related to the double calcination-step needed for the capture of the CO₂ from the limestone fed into the pre-calciner: indeed, CO₂ released in the pre-calciner by the raw meal calcination is converted to CaCO₃ in the carbonator of the CaL process, which is calcined again in the oxyfuel calciner.

On the other hand, the higher direct fuel consumption, the higher the power generated and consequently the lower the *indirect primary energy consumption* (q_c), as depicted in Fig. 5:

- the tail end CaL 20%-IL configuration shows the lowest q_c (-0.82 MJ_{LHV}/kg_{clik}). This value is negative as the cement plant is a net exporter of carbon-free electricity;
- in the tail end CaL 50%-IL and integrated CaL configurations there is a moderate variation of the electricity consumption, by approximately -53% and +35% of the reference cement plant.
- in both the full and partial oxyfuel configurations, the power generated in the bottoming cycle is much lower than the electric consumption of the ASU and CPU. As reported breakdown of Fig. 6, the power generated in the oxyfuel configurations can only cover 10.0% (full oxyfuel) and 21.8% (partial oxyfuel) of the additional power demand, causing a significant increase of the indirect primary energy consumption and CO₂ emissions.

Finally, the combination of the direct fuel consumption and indirect primary energy consumption results in a moderate increase in *equivalent primary energy consumption* in full oxyfuel (+31.0%) and in partial oxyfuel (+41.3%) configurations. A more significant increase in equivalent primary energy consumption can be seen in the integrated CaL (+59.7%) and tail end CaL (+84.9% and +77.7% in 20%-IL and 50%-IL respectively) configurations.

Fig. 5 Break-down of equivalent primary energy consumption of the different configurations

Fig. 6 Break-down of electric consumption of the different configurations

5.2. Direct, Indirect and equivalent CO₂ Emissions

Fig. 7 shows the specific CO₂ emissions of all the configurations. Simulation results show that:

- the integrated CaL configuration achieves the lowest direct CO₂ emissions and, therefore, the highest value of the direct CO₂ emission reduction (94.2%).
- the partial oxyfuel configuration achieves the highest direct CO₂ emissions (corresponding to a reduction of about 79%), because only the CO₂ generated by calcination and combustion in the pre-calciner is sent to the CPU and to storage /utilization, whereas the CO₂ generated in the rotary kiln is emitted.
- the full oxyfuel configuration features a direct CO₂ emission reduction of about 92%, as all the CO₂ generated in the process is sent to the CPU and all the residual emission is attributable to the CPU vent gas.

- in the tail end CaL, the carbonator treats the entire CO₂ generated by the clinker production process. Since part of the limestone is replaced with lime from the purge of the CaL system, the reduction of CO₂ emissions at the stack is greater than the carbonator capture efficiency. The tail end CaL 50%-IL achieves a direct emission reduction of 91.2%, while, in the tail end CaL 20%-IL, the CO₂ from the CPU vent gas adversely affects the direct emission reduction, which is equal to 87.1%.

The indirect CO₂ emissions are associated with the indirect primary energy consumption in the system and therefore the same considerations as above apply.

As a result, all the CaL configurations, achieve equivalent emission reduction of about 90%. Only the tail end CaL 20%-IL results in a greater equivalent emission reduction than the direct emission reduction, thanks to the net electricity generated. The equivalent emission reductions for all other configurations are negatively affected by indirect emissions. The indirect CO₂ emissions represent about 53%, 48%, 29% and 17% of the equivalent CO₂ emissions for the full oxyfuel, integrated CaL, partial oxyfuel and tail end CaL 50%-IL respectively.

Fig. 7 Break-down of equivalent CO₂ emission of the different configurations analyzed

5.3. SPECCA

Fig. 8 summarizes the resulting SPECCA index of the different configurations, as well as its breakdown into the main contributions.

The full oxyfuel configuration achieves the lowest SPECCA among the considered options, thanks to a high reduction of the direct CO₂ emissions, even if the large amount of electricity required for the process negatively affects the equivalent primary energy consumption and the equivalent CO₂ emissions. On the contrary, the highest SPECCA is achieved for the Tail End configuration, due to the high fuel consumption in the CaL calciner.

Fig. 8 Break-down of SPECCA of the different configurations analysed

The most important contributions to the SPECCA differ among the configurations:

- For the integrated CaL configuration the main contribution is related to the increase in fuel consumption in the oxy-calculator. The electricity generated is not enough to sustain the total power demand of the system and a reduction in equivalent CO₂ avoided is achieved.
- For the tail end CaL configuration, the main contribution is related to the large amount of fuel consumption in the system. Depending on the IL, it is possible to obtain a positive net electricity generation, which contributes to reduce both added equivalent primary energy consumption and equivalent CO₂ emissions.
- For the full oxyfuel configuration, the added equivalent primary energy consumption and the reduction in equivalent CO₂ avoided are almost entirely due to the increase in electric power consumption.
- For the partial oxyfuel configuration the added equivalent primary energy consumption and the reduction in equivalent CO₂ avoided are related to the increase in the total fuel consumption and the total power demand of the system.

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